

MASSCA: SCALABLE MULTI-AGENT SYSTEM FRAMEWORK FOR SMART POWER CELL CO-SIMULATION

Danila Valko, Sharaf Alsharif, Deborah Tolk and Tobias Grimm

R&D Division Energy
OFFIS – Institute for Information Technology
Oldenburg, Germany
E-mail: danila.valko@offis.de

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ABSTRACT

The power system is becoming increasingly complex due to the rise of distributed renewable energy sources and controllable loads such as batteries and electric vehicles. To effectively manage such complexity, a cellular approach emerges as a promising strategy, organising the system into cells that autonomously balance power locally while interacting with neighbouring cells. However, ensuring secure and reliable operation in such complex power systems demands comprehensive simulations of both the power system models and the necessary communication infrastructure between cells, along with their associated algorithms before testing in the field. Co-simulation approaches are positional to address such a problem. This work demonstrates utilising open-source tools to simulate cellular power grids effectively. We present a co-simulation framework that includes a multi-agent system simulator for cellular distributed power systems. The framework enables the development of heterogeneous scenarios with a wide range of energy system components and adaptors supported by the *mosaik* ecosystem. Moreover, it enables simultaneous peer-to-peer (between-cell) and hierarchical (within-cell) agent interaction with user-defined behaviour. We validate our solution using a scenario that is derived from the European configuration of the medium voltage distribution networks and perform computational experiments that confirm the high scalability of the proposed solution.

INTRODUCTION

With the increasing share of distributed generation and volatile renewable energy resources, the power system complexity is undergoing a rapid increase. Furthermore, the integration of more controllable loads, including batteries, electric vehicles, heat pumps, and electrolyzers, further compounds this complexity. Hence, an intelligent power system control becomes more significant for

an efficient and stable system, but also more complex and challenging.

One approach to address the intricacies in an evolving power system is the cellular approach (Bayer et al. 2019). The power system is logically divided into cells, which try to operate autonomously by balancing their power generation and consumption locally. For the remaining imbalance, the cells cooperate with neighbouring cells to exchange power (Dengler et al. 2022). Cells can be also grouped hierarchically into larger cells. If an imbalance cannot be solved on one level, it is forwarded to the next hierarchy level. This helps to solve the increasing complexity that comes with an increasing amount of flexibility in the power system (Bogdanov et al. 2023, Bayer et al. 2019).

Secure and reliable operation under such complex interactions requires the use of more advanced power system modelling, simulation tools and techniques (Badrzadeh et al. 2020). Approaches and algorithms such as the cellular approach need to be tested in-depth to understand their behaviour and impact on the power system. Co-simulation has evolved as an integral tool of research and development in power systems (Alfalouji et al. 2023, Selvaraj et al. 2023). For instance, the cellular approach requires running a simulation comprising models from different domains, such as PV and wind generators, controllers, the electric grid model and even electro-chemical models as in batteries and electrolyzers. Running these simulations with a monolithic tool requires detailed knowledge of these models and lacks flexibility. In this regard, the concept of co-simulation allows coupling heterogeneous software tools and models which are already developed by the respective domain experts. This approach greatly reduces the modelling effort and error-proneness compared to monolithic representations of multidisciplinary systems (Steinbrink et al. 2019). Furthermore, multi-agent systems (MAS) solutions for the interaction between system components in the power system context can be combined with the co-simulation approach to address the complexity of such system (Steinbrink et al. 2019).

In this work, we present an implementation of the power cell concept with open-source tools for power system co-simulation and MAS. We also demonstrate the perfor-

Figure 1: The power cell concept illustrated on part of the CIGRE Task Force C6.04.0 network. Based on (Bayer et al. 2019, Dengler et al. 2022): Ellipses represent logically and/or geographically separated hierarchical or peer-to-peer parts of the power network that are organised as power cells.

mance and scalability through a use case.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: the background section provides a review of the theoretical background of the cellular approach for power systems and the role of multi-agent systems. The methods section describes the methodology, the structure and principles of the proposed framework. In the use case section, a use-case scenario and the results of the scalability experiments are presented. Finally, the paper provides a conclusion and future work.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

The Cellular Approach and the Power Cell Concept

The general cell-based approach for energy and power systems is well described in recent literature. According to (Bayer et al. 2019) an energy cell (EC) is a kind of logically isolated energy infrastructure including all equipment used for energy conversion, transportation, distribution and storage. ECs are used to build an energy system of any scope and the cell structure is repeated at all levels of the energy system. Neighbouring cells can be arranged hierarchically, so there are cells at the same level as well as superimposed and subordinate levels (Fig. 1).

The control of a cell includes all the technological control equipment, including the necessary communication technologies. Control is generally performed to maintain the operational state of the network (network pro-

tection, voltage regulation, etc.) as well as to maintain the energy balance. This can, for example, be done periodically or dynamically and result in three states: balanced, over-supplied or under-supplied across all available forms of energy or power flows (Bayer et al. 2019). The cell control is also responsible for implementing measures to prevent network outages, as well as for carrying out necessary load reductions and energy reductions, and for fault-related switching.

An EC encapsulates geographically or structurally coherent parts of an energy system of any scale (Dengler et al. 2022). In an EC there is a producer, a consumer, and a storage component which are connected to a controller agent that can control the exchange of energy and information. According to (Dengler et al. 2022) the controller might be local which is localised on the top of some cell component or can be hierarchical which is considered as an agent outside a certain cell and able to control a number of cells. The goal of an EC (and a controller) is to fulfil its own needs but is furthermore able to exchange energy with connected ECs (Dengler et al. 2022).

A similar approach to mention here is the smart power cell concept (SPC) which is specifically related to a grid subsection composed of a set of power conversion units interconnected by a 3-phase AC-grid (Gonzalez et al. 2020). The monitoring and control system supervises the behaviour of SPCs by considering only aggregated information regarding their interfaces. It issues aggregated control instructions when adjustments are needed for the behaviour of a specific SPC at a transmission network bus to influence the operating state of the transmission network. A SPC-based infrastructure has internal and external objectives. The main internal objectives: to supervise the voltage profiles, loading limits, and local stability limits to optimise the operation of the SPC according to technical and economic criteria (Gonzalez et al. 2020). The main external objectives are to coordinate the dynamic behaviour in a supportive way, the flexibility to deliberately influence the active and reactive power exchange with the transmission network, to estimate and provide forecasts of the available flexibility and to adjust the active and reactive power flow exchanged with the transmission network etc (Gonzalez et al. 2020).

Thus, previous research has successfully explored the cellular concept for distributed power systems and delved into the operational aspects and control strategies involved in managing power interactions within such systems (Gonzalez et al. 2020, Rasti and Schegner 2023). (Gonzalez et al. 2020) has been focused on the cross-voltage interaction and the dynamic behaviour, while the flexibility-related questions and power balance in multi-modal energy cells were investigated in (Rasti and Schegner 2023, Wiegel et al. 2023, Dengler et al. 2022). As this paper reviews the basics needed from the previous work regarding the cellular approach to deliver

the co-simulation framework idea, we consider *energy*-, *smart*- and *power*- cells as synonyms.

The Multi-Agent Smart Systems for Power Cells

Multi-agent systems (MAS) in general are smart systems, for optimised control and management, where complex computational and optimisation problems are broken over many entities, known as agents (Kantamneni et al. 2015). In the context of the cellular approach, distributed power systems and energy resources (DER), MAS is a set of agents that should collaborate to achieve both local and global objectives (Tazi et al. 2020), e.g. decrease operational costs, increase user comfort, maintain a functional state of the network, etc. For this purpose, an agent should learn and analyse the environment, update its local state, and react to local events autonomously which is usually difficult to define analytically, involves Distributed Problem Solving (DPS) and Distributed Artificial Intelligence (DAI) (Tazi et al. 2020, Colson and Nehrir 2013). Discussing the advantages of MAS itself for power system applications is not in the scope of this work, but they are widely discussed in several papers (see, for instance, (Boussaada et al. 2016, Kantamneni et al. 2015, Colson and Nehrir 2013), etc.).

The proposal of using MAS for cooperative multi-criteria flexibility optimisation within the context of smart buildings was highlighted in (Nieße and Tröschel 2016, Nebel-Wenner et al. 2019). They developed a multi-agent framework named ISAAC for distributed optimisation, which proves useful both for aggregating DERs for virtual power plants and for smart control within distribution grids. This framework is built upon a lightweight MAS Python library *aiomas* (see at <https://aiomas.readthedocs.io/>). Their methodology aligns with ours in that it also considers independent agents, where each agent represents a single energy unit (in their case, a smart building) and employs a co-simulation design. Therefore, this approach is effective for peer-to-peer communication and could serve as an optimisation algorithm for top-level cell agents. However, they did not account for hierarchical topologies, limiting its applicability for intra-cell agent interactions, and they did not incorporate power network models into simulation scenarios.

In (Colson and Nehrir 2013), a power management scenario for a multi-asset microgrid employing a self-organising MAS was presented. Their implementation utilised *MATLAB/Simulink*, and *JADE* (Java Agent Development framework) (Khalid et al. 2020). Their concept of power management primarily focused on asset dispatch for the static stability of the grid, incorporating near real-time simulation with a 100 ms timestep. During asset instantiation in their simulation environment, a corresponding agent (producer, consumer, or observer) is initiated and linked with its asset,

restricted to observing information directly measurable at the asset itself. In their framework, MAS serves as the decision-making core of the microgrid, with agent communications typically being peer-to-peer, thereby simulating inter-cell interaction. However, a single agent is not designed to represent a collection of intellectual assets with varying behaviours.

Another *JADE*-based software tool for developing and operating MAS was introduced in (Derksen et al. 2011). The idea behind this solution was to provide a graphical end-user application that makes the powerful but not very user-friendly *JADE* framework manageable for non-computer scientists. In their further work (Loose et al. 2020), a concept of unified energy agents and the energy option model were introduced. Using a simulation of coupled electrical and district heating networks they showed that the energy agents approach is applicable for simulation and optimisation of cross-sectoral scenarios.

Furthermore, several studies have explored specific solutions for dynamic supply-demand matching (Pournaras et al. 2009), day-ahead scheduling tasks (Hinrichs et al. 2014), multi-object optimisation for power plants (Bremer and Lehnhoff 2019), and re-dispatch measures for neighbourhood grids (Acosta et al. 2023), all through the lens of agent-based paradigms. However, these works do not offer a toolkit for a cellular approach, making it technically challenging or even impossible to adapt their software for use with the wide range of simulators and components available either in the *MATLAB/Simulink* or *mosaik* ecosystem. Nonetheless, as we provide an analysis and co-simulation open framework, the communication protocols and optimisation techniques proposed in the aforementioned works could be integrated into an open library of our solution for further evaluation of applicability within a cellular approach.

MULTI-AGENT SYSTEM FRAMEWORK FOR POWER CELL CO-SIMULATION

The Multi-Agent System Simulator and the Co-Simulation Framework

In implementing the cell model and its communication layer, we followed the general cell-based approach that is described above. Our MASS is developed as a modular part of the *mosaik* co-simulation framework that allows one to reuse and combine existing simulation models and simulators to create large-scale scenarios (Steinbrink et al. 2019). *mosaik* is a well-known validated framework that is useful when dealing with complex systems having a high number of interactions (Barbierato et al. 2022) that we want to contain inside the MAS. Thus, developed scenarios can serve as a test bed for various types of control strategies (e.g., multi-agent systems or centralised control). MASS itself is based on the Python

mango (Schrage et al. 2023) library that supports Agent Communication Language messages and allows one to create lightweight agents with complex behaviour.

MASS is designed as a component that allows a user to easily create a large number of agents, connect them into hierarchical structures, and define their behaviour directly in the simulation scenario. Since the cell simulation involves a variety of components and heterogeneous simulators, agents can be connected to any type of component or simulator via the *mosaik* API. The user must define in advance what data the agents will be able to collect and exchange and how that data should be aggregated when transmitted across hierarchy levels within and between the cells.

To simulate cell control, the user must also define a control algorithm. This can be either a centralised algorithm or a peer-to-peer communication protocol. To make this possible, all top-level (cell) agents are by default not connected to each other, but to the root *mosaik* agent. This allows to critically reduce the complexity of communication and this agent also serves as a *mosaik* interface, so that all the connections can be defined within the co-simulation scenario (Fig. 2).

In the case of a centralised control algorithm, the *mosaik* agent acts as a top-level controller and, with all the necessary information received, runs the algorithm and then broadcasts instructions to the cell agents. In the case of a decentralised control and communication protocol, the *mosaik* agent is treated as a monitoring node, nevertheless initiating a communication loop between the cell agents at each simulation step and waiting for confirmation of their readiness. Such a solution ensures synchronisation within the co-simulation and with the *mosaik* scheduler.

The cell agents aggregate the output from connected agents and then pass it among themselves to develop internal instructions. The *mosaik* agent provides updates from simulated entities (power units or other linked simulators) to its associated agents, triggers a communication cycle, broadcasts instructions and waits for confirmation messages. For simplicity, *mosaik* synchronously updates the agents with data from associated entities (Fig. 3), but it is possible to do it asynchronously, using an event-based paradigm.

The Multi-Agent System Simulator Configuration

In addition to using the standard *mosaik* scenario definition detailed in its documentation (see at <https://mosaik.readthedocs.io/en/latest/scenario-definition.html>), the user has to define a configuration of MASS directly in the scenario.

The required configuration methods that must be defined depend on the user's and the scenario goals: *input_method*, which transforms *mosaik* inputs to the agent state; *output_method*, which transforms the agent

state back to *mosaik* outputs; *states_agg_method*, which aggregates states that are collected at each hierarchical level to make an aggregated state; and *execute_method*, which must implement a control strategy or communication protocol and/or execute (simulate the execution) the received re-dispatch instructions for linked power unit.

We have defined default methods that meet the idea of communicating the simplest version of unit flexibility and implemented an altruistic strategy for the cell agents that are described in the next section. A detailed description of the solution as well as necessary UML diagrams can be found in the public repository (available at <https://gitlab.com/hybit1/massca>).

USE CASE SCENARIO AND SCALABILITY EXPERIMENTS

The Use Case Co-Simulation Scenario

The co-simulation scenario is derived from the capacity expansion pathways for wind and solar PV as projected in the German network development plan for 2032 (NEP 2012). It consists of two components (Fig. 2): (1) A power network that is modelled with *pan-dapower* (Thurner et al. 2018) and a set of PV/Wind power simulators that are linked to related units in the power network. (2) A multi-agent system that consists of one agent for each simulated power unit, m hierarchical agents, and n top-level agents (cell agents) that represent the cellular (aggregated) level.

The power network model comprises models of conventional power plants, conventional and flexible loads, distributed generators, OLTC transformers and circuit breakers. The model is implemented using the *SimBench* Power System library (e.g, particularly CIGRE Task Force C6.04.02 (CIGRE 2014)), which is based on the European configuration of the high and medium voltage distribution networks benchmark described in (Meincke et al. 2020, CIGRE 2014). Thus, each modelled cell in this scenario is defined as a logically separated medium voltage sub-network with PV and Wind DER. This configuration was chosen due to the fact that it is complex enough to model and study several phenomena which could occur in a real power system (e.g. power imbalance, frequency and voltage instability etc.) while its limited size enables the traceability of the system's behaviour (Gonzalez et al. 2020).

In the scenario, the agents observe the power outputs and flexibility provided by associated power units in the network such as generators, loads etc. The cell agents aggregate outputs from connected agents and then pass them among themselves to collaborate and develop new set points, as well as internal instructions. So, we defined *state* (S_i) of an i -th agent/unit as a data structure consisting of a flexibility snapshot: the minimum and maximum active power, and the current power measure-

Figure 2: Co-simulation scenario decomposition showing the connection of the PV, Wind and flexible load simulators (*sim*) to the corresponding agents (A) in a multi-agent simulator and to the power system model. The agents are interconnected in such a way as to represent the cellular topology of the grid. All simulators and connections are managed by *mosaik* and defined in a standard *mosaik* scenario.

Figure 3: The message exchange between *mosaik* and the MASS at every simulation time step during the co-simulation

ment for a certain time step. An aggregation function that is called by $m + n$ agents at each hierarchical level was defined as summation: $S_{agg} = agg(S_i) = \sum S_i$. For illustration, in this paper, a strict altruistic communication strategy was employed (for details see, e.g. (Colson and Nehrir 2013)). Under this strategy, the agents share information about their flexibility and needs. The cell agent with less flexibility tries to fulfil its needs with intra-cellular power, if this is not possible, it asks neighbour cell agent(s) to assist. The remaining lack of power is replenished by the external network. Accordingly, intra-cellular instructions consist of the first feasible set points for each power unit within each cell. We did not specify the execution of instructions for each unit so that they report confirmation of received instruc-

tions anyway (see Fig. 3).

Scalability Experiments

To test the scalability of our MASS for the cellular approach (MASSCA) and to represent a number of power cells, a larger network was created including multiple sub-networks that are based on the CIGRE benchmark grid, the networks are connected to one single transmission network. We also randomised the cell/unit flexibility profiles, randomly added hierarchical agents and shuffled connections between the agents and related units in each cell to obtain a hierarchy of different levels. In this way, we can vary the number of cells (n) along with the levels of the hierarchy (h) by having the same number of power units per cell. This is necessary to fairly compare the computational complexity that MASS with different topologies adds to the co-simulation scenario.

To perform computational experiments, we varied the number of cells $n = 5, 10, 15, \dots, 50$ and the hierarchy depth $h = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 10$ and estimated the total execution time for each combination and the total agent interaction time during which MASS performs its simulation step (Fig. 4).

We ran five simulations per each combination of (h, n) with a different random seed and shuffled cells hierarchy. Each simulated cell is made of a CIGRE-based sub-network consisting of 18 loads, 8 PV and 1 WP, lines, buses, switches and trafos as in (PP 2022). The number of cells and the hierarchy depths are chosen taking into account other works on smart grids (Tazi et al. 2020) and power cells simulations (Dengler et al. 2022, Gonzalez et al. 2020) as well as real sub-network sizes (see *Simbench* LV example grids at <https://simbench.de>).

Figure 4: The average total scenario execution time and agent interaction time with a hierarchy depth (h) and a cell count (n) are shown: (a): $h = 1$, (b): $n = 50$. Each data point represents one simulation of 24 hours duration with 15-minute time steps. The shaded area represents the 95% confidence interval for the fitted line.

As can be seen from the results (Fig. 4), the experimental estimates agree with the theoretical considerations for our use case. Since in our example we use a simple re-dispatch strategy and a summation-based flexibility aggregation is applied at each level of the hierarchy, the theoretical time complexity must be $O(n)$. In the case of a deep hierarchy, the complexity will be as for *Breadth First Search* - $O(b^h)$, where b is the branching factor. Of course, the linear complexity may deteriorate if a more complex control algorithm or communication protocol is to be implemented. In any case, we have demonstrated that the *mosaik* and MASS do not deteriorate the theoretical expectations and have a good scalability potential.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, we presented a co-simulation framework that includes MASSCA (the Multi-Agent Systems Simulator for Cellular Approach) for distributed power systems. It enables the development of heterogeneous co-simulation scenarios with a wide range of energy system components and adapters supported by the *mosaik* ecosystem, and enables simultaneous peer-to-peer (between-cell) and hierarchical (within-cell) agent interaction with user-defined behaviour. We also described a simplified use case and performed computational experiments that confirmed the high scalability of the proposed solution.

Since we have developed a MAS simulator component as part of the *mosaik* ecosystem, we expect that the Energy and Research community will be able to extend its capabilities and/or convey further requests for development. Our next steps in research include developing and implementing specific control strategies to optimize energy flow within and between neighboring cells. This entails investigating algorithms for dynamic load management, energy distribution, and network stabilization at the cellular level. We want to implement and adapt two well-known protocols and algorithms for independent agents to maintain the functional state of the distributed power system.

One of them is called COHDA (the Combinatorial Optimization Heuristic for Distributed Agents) – it is based on self-organisation strategies and yields a distributed combinatorial optimisation process in an asynchronous communication environment, the correctness of COHDA with respect to convergence and termination is proven formally (Hinrichs et al. 2014, Bremer and Lehnhoff 2019).

Another one is called LPEP (the Lightweight Power Exchange Protocol) – a lightweight protocol that has been designed to provide a set of behavioural rules for the universal smart grid agent, to define the data necessary to adhere to those rules, and is able to solve the demand-supply calculation which selects other nodes' offers and ensures the power equilibrium at each part of the power

grid(Veith et al. 2014). Finally, we will simulate realistic scenarios to evaluate and validate the performance and applicability of MASSCA with considering various operational conditions and disturbances to assess the robustness of our approaches.

We also encourage researchers and developers to join in the extension of the algorithm library for the cellular approach and the development of this toolkit.

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CODE AND DATA AVAILABILITY

All data and algorithms used can be found in the public repository at <https://gitlab.com/hybit1/massca>

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